

Parachor and Chemical Constitution. Part V. The Structure of "Liquid Crystals".

BY SUSIL KUMAR RAY.

In spite of a great amount of investigations on the structure of the anisotropic liquids, the initial change of these substances on heating into the mesomorphic or cloudy state is not yet clearly understood. The work of Vorlander, Bose and various other investigators have shown that on melting, the cohesion between the molecules, which previously held them in the crystal arrangement, does not break down uniformly in all directions. There may be a lateral cohesion which still exists, which will tend to hold the molecules in bundles. This makes the liquid anisotropic. It was thought that the determination of the parachor of these substances at different temperatures might be helpful in the elucidation of this problem. From a perusal of the literature it was found that Jager (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1917, **101**, 1) determined the surface tension and density of some of these compounds over wide ranges of temperatures. In the present paper the parachor of these substances has been calculated from Jager's data, and an attempt has been made to explain the change from the mesomorphic state to the clear liquid state from a knowledge of the parachor.

In the following tables the parachor of azoxybenzene, *p*-azoxyanisole, *p*-azoxyphenetole and *p*-methoxybenzalazine at different temperatures have been calculated. Though azoxybenzene is not a liquid crystal, its parachor is given as a basis for comparison. In the last column of the Tables I, II, and III the parachor has been calculated on the assumption that the azoxy compounds contain the grouping $\begin{array}{c} \text{---N=N---} \\ \downarrow \\ \text{O} \end{array}$ and is confirmed from the results in Table I.

TABLE I.

Azoxybenzene.

$P_{\text{calc.}} = 446.6.$

Temp.	Surface tension.	Density.	$P_{\text{obs.}}$	Temp.	Surface tension.	Density.	$P_{\text{obs.}}$
55.8°	39.3	1.133	437.5	115°	34.7	1.087	442.2
70.6	38.3	1.121	439.4	130.5	33.5	1.074	443.5
85.0	37.1	1.110	440.2	145.5	32.1	1.063	443.3
100	35.9	1.098	441.5	162	30.8	1.050	444.2

TABLE II.

p-Azoxyanisole.

$$P_{\text{calc.}} = 564.6$$

Temp.	Surface tension.	Density.	$P_{\text{obs.}}$	Temp.	Surface tension.	Density.	$P_{\text{obs.}}$
115°	40.1	1.171	554.6	144.5°	37.2	1.136	561.0
120	39.0	1.166	552.0	155.2	36.0	1.126	561.5
126	37.7	1.159	550.7	160.5	35.5	1.124	560.7
129.5	36.4	1.156	548.6	174.5	34.2	1.112	561.3
133.5	37.8	1.152	555.6	190	33.0	1.100	562.3
138.1	37.9	1.142	560.8	211	31.4	1.080	565.7

TABLE III.

p-Azoxyphenetole.

$$P_{\text{calc.}} = 642.6.$$

Temp.	Surface tension.	Density.	$P_{\text{obs.}}$	Temp.	Surface tension.	Density.	$P_{\text{obs.}}$
142.5°	31.6	1.094	620.3	168.5°	29.3	1.068	623.6
147.5	30.7	1.089	618.6	174.5	28.6	1.053	628.7
151.8	30.0	1.084	618.0	190	27.3	1.039	629.5
159	29.0	1.076	617.3	205	26.2	1.026	631.4
164	28.3	1.072	615.9	219	25.2	1.014	632.5

TABLE IV.

p-Methoxybenzalazine.

$$P_{\text{calc.}} = 613.2.$$

Temp.	Surface tension.	Density.	$P_{\text{obs.}}$	Temp.	Surface tension.	Density.	$P_{\text{obs.}}$
171°	32.1	1.051	607.1	180.5°	31.2	1.035	612.4
173.5	31.4	1.049	604.9	185	30.4	1.031	610.6
174.5	31.1	1.048	604.0	195	29.2	1.023	609.2
176.5	30.5	1.046	602.3	204.5	28.3	1.015	609.4
178	29.9	1.044	600.5	219	27.4	1.002	612.3
179	29.4	1.043	598.5	230.5	26.8	0.993	614.4

The variation of the parachor with temperature becomes strikingly evident from the following curves drawn by plotting P_{obs} against the corresponding temperatures (the number of the curves corresponds with that of the table).

It will be observed from the above tables and the curves, that the parachor of the liquid crystals varies with the temperature. The parachor at first decreases gradually, reaches a minimum value and then just a few degrees before the transition point it increases abruptly and attains a value about 12-14 units higher at the true melting point and then increases gradually with the increase of temperature. This abrupt rise in the parachor can only be explained on the assumption that in the mesomorphic state the molecules are greatly associated. No other constitutional change in the molecule will be sufficient to account for this rise of about 12 units in the parachor. As the true melting point is reached, the lateral cohesion which still exists between the molecules, breaks down and the molecules become less complex. This increase of about 12 units in the parachor at the transition point can

easily be explained on the assumption that in the mesomorphic state seven or eight molecules are associated to form a complex molecule (for then the parachor decrease will be $7 \times 14.4/8$ or 12.6 units, Sidgwick, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1461). The variations in the parachor at temperatures above the melting point may be explained on the assumption that the molecules are still slightly associated, and this association diminishes with the rise of temperatures; with azoxybenzene this phenomenon is also observed.

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Negative Ferric Hydroxide Sol. A Modified Method of its Preparation.

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Powis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 818) describes a simple method for the preparation of negative ferric hydroxide sol. This sol contains, however, an excess of alkali which evidently has a stabilising influence on it. Our attempt was directed to replace the superfluous alkali by another electrolyte, neutral in character, and possessing at the same time a stabilising influence on the sol. We required such a neutral sol for extracting uranium-X from uranyl salts. In this attempt we have found a few electrolytes possessing stabilising action. They are characterised from the other (similarly examined) electrolytes in giving iron salts, stable in an alkaline medium. It is generalised therefrom that an electrolyte, which gives an iron salt, stable in an alkaline medium, has a stabilising action on negative ferric hydroxide sol.

The substances found to possess a stabilising action are potassium citrate, potassium tartrate, potassium carbonate, potassium sulphide, sodium phosphate and sodium silicate. The citrate and the tartrate